

THE EFFECT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ON THE COGNITIVE ABILITY OF STUDENTS

Ruziev Feruz Giyosovich

Assistant of the Department of Rehabilitation, Sports Medicine and Physical
Education, Bukhara State Medical Institute, PhD,

Chorieva Aziza Umed qizi

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Faculty of Medicine,
student of the 3rd stage of treatment

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12578754>

ANNOTATION

Based on a medical questionnaire and medical examinations among the students of the Bukhara State Medical Institute of the 3rd level, it was studied whether the nutritional characteristics of the students are related to the frequency of gastrointestinal diseases and their nutritional norms.

Key words: Students healthy lifestyle, nutrition, diseases of the digestive system

Introduction: Students' health status is pressing problem of modern society. The basis of health protection and preservation any person, including students, the dominant role is played by the image and way of life life. A characteristic feature of student youth is a low level of responsibility for their own health [1]. The problem of nutrition today is relevant as for all segments of the population and for all levels of education, starting from preschool and ending with postgraduate [2]. Analysis of the components of students' lifestyle shows that individual components have a very pronounced significance. So, nutrition accounts for 10–15% of the time, motor activity 15–30% of the time is spent on activity, and 24–30% of the time is spent on sleep. And since these processes last for 5–6 years of study, then they have a significant impact on the health of students [3].

Research objective: Studying the relationship between students' nutritional characteristics and the development of gastrointestinal diseases in them.

Research materials and methods. The results of examination and analysis of 58 students of the Bukhara State Medical Institute in 2023-2024 were presented in order to solve the scientific goals and tasks envisaged by our research work. Students were divided into 3 groups who had breakfast, those who did not have a full breakfast, and those who had a full breakfast, and the occurrence of gastrointestinal diseases in them was studied.

Analysis and results. It was studied that the students' lifestyle is not in the same order, they do not follow the sleep schedule, they do not wake up early in

the morning, and they eat breakfast in a hurry, which causes the violation of nutrition standards. It was also studied that the fact that most students live in student housing or rent instead of at home, and that students have to prepare breakfast by themselves, causes disruption of the students' breakfast routines. The students were divided into groups that did not eat breakfast n=12, 20,7±1,6 did not eat a full breakfast n=26, 44,8±2,4 , and did not eat a full breakfast n=20, 34,5±2,1. The indicators of occurrence of gastrointestinal diseases in students of these groups were studied (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Figure 1. Grouping of students according to the order of breakfast.

It was found that 39.6% of the students in the research group had various digestive system pathologies such as chronic gastritis, dyspepsia and dysbacteriosis. (Fig. 2).

Figure 2.

of gastrointestinal diseases were observed in 66.7% of cases, 53.8% in the second group and 25% in the third group.

Conclusion: Proper nutrition, which is one of the important principles of a healthy lifestyle, and especially a full breakfast, causes a decrease in gastrointestinal complications..

References:

1. I.N. Shuvalova, M. N. Popov, Formirovaniye zdorovogo obraza jizni studentov: vozmojniye puti resheniya problemi pitaniya – 2016 No. 4 (46) – Chast 7,179, – P.114-119.
2. Svetkina A.A. Psikhologicheskaya rehabilitation bolnyx s ONMK, // Meditsinskaya psikhologiya v Rossii, — 2016, — T. 8, No. 5, — S. 7.
3. Wenli Chen, Qian Ye, Xiangtong Ji, Sicong Zhang, Xi Yang. Mirror neuron system based therapy for aphasia rehabilitation, // Frontiers in Psychology, October 2015, Volume 6, R.1-11.
4. Jenny K Burton, Terence J Quinn, Miles Fisher. Diabetes and stroke, // Practical Diabetes 2019, 36(4), P.126-131.
5. Jabborovna TY, Giyosovich RF The Influence of Adverse Climate Regions on the Complication of Hypertension Disease //Genius Repository. - 2023. - T. 27. - S. 128-132.
6. Feruz R. i dr. The Importance of Early Rehabilitation in the Prevention of Hemorrhagic Stroke Complications // SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF PRACTICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES. - 2023. - T. 2. – no. 12. - S. 989-996.

